

Training and Accompaniment of Primary School Accreditation

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Abstract— Schools accreditation is an assessment activity to determine the eligibility of schools conducting the learning process. Accreditation is an external quality assurance system as part of the education quality assurance system. Accreditation is important for schools because with the status of accreditation it will have an impact on the acquisition of the number of students and the composition of teachers in the primary schools concerned. Accreditation is also a form of an external quality assurance system, a process used by authorized institutions to provide formal recognition that an institution has the ability to carry out certain activities. Schools that have been accredited receive greater recognition in the community compared to schools that have not been accredited. The better the accreditation, the more positive the student's decision to choose the school. The purpose of activities is to provide training accompanied by an accreditation process in primary schools in Samarinda city. It is hoped that this activity will assist schools in developing schools accreditation forms and provide benefits by increasing the accreditation ranking in elementary schools in Samarinda city.

Keywords— Accreditation, primary schools.

I. INTRODUCTION

The process of selecting schools by prospective students is a big decision, because it is a long-term decision that will affect the lives of students. This choice can affect a student's future career, future social life and student's personal satisfaction. In the perspective of prospective students, the decision to choose a school is considered to have the potential to change the lives of individuals. Therefore, the decision to choose the school is an important issue.

Competition that occurs between schools, both public and private, forces schools to continuously improve the strategic approach to increase input of new students in the school concerned. With increasingly fierce competition, then schools must be more vigorous in conducting promotions and improving quality in order to remain the choice of students to continue their education. It is very important for a school to always maintain and improve its quality so that it becomes the first choice for students who will take part in the learning and education process in a school.

Accreditation is an external quality assurance system as part of the school quality assurance system. Accreditation is important for both public and private schools because accreditation status will have an impact on the acquisition of the number of students and the composition of teachers at the school concerned. Accreditation is also a form of an external quality assurance system, a process used by authorized

institutions to provide formal recognition that an institution has the ability to carry out certain activities.

Accreditation ranks in several schools greatly affect the assessment given to the school concerned. With the increasingly diverse conditions and requirements needed, schools need careful preparation to apply for the school accreditation process. Based on the existing conditions, it is felt necessary to carry out training and mentoring activities for the leaders and the team composing accreditation forms for elementary schools.

Accreditation is an acknowledgment of a school that shows that the school in implementing the education program and the quality of graduates produced has met the standards set by the National Accreditation Board for Schools/Madrasah [1]. This shows that schools that have been accredited receive greater recognition in the community compared to schools that have not been accredited.

Accreditation is carried out on schools based on interactions between standards in the National Education Standards. The accreditation process is stated with the school's accreditation status that is accredited and not accredited. At present the leadership and the team making up the school accreditation forms in several elementary schools in Samarinda city still experience difficulties in preparing the school accreditation forms. This of course will affect the future of the relevant school graduates. To provide guarantees to stakeholders the school must always strive to improve the quality of the learning process. One way is to carry out the accreditation process so that schools that have not been able to get good ratings can re-accredit them to improve the accreditation rank of the school concerned.

Based on the description that has been stated above, there are problems that can be formulated and intended to be resolved in this community service activity, namely how training and assistance can be provided to elementary schools in Samarinda that will carry out the accreditation process so that the school gets a good accreditation rating.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

Accreditation is the process of evaluating and assessing the quality of an institution or study program carried out by a team of peer experts (assessors) based on established quality standards, at the direction of an independent accreditation board or institution outside the relevant institution or study program. The results of accreditation is an acknowledgment that an institution or study program has met the established

quality standards, so that it is feasible to carry out its programs.

External monitoring institutions [2] through accreditation and certification [3] are a form of Quality Assurance mechanism (QA) facilitated to assess the level of quality and compliance with identified local and international quality standards such as increased use of ISO 9001 which shows that the concept of quality used is driven by external market requirements [4].

The QA mechanism undoubtedly ignites enthusiasm of members of the organization to move to higher levels of manifestation of quality [5] and failure to recognize different dimensions can reduce institutional goals [4]. This has slowly but surely become an integral part of most education systems [6]. United State Approach for quality assurance consists of credentials at the individual level, including certification, and at the institutional level, including regional and program-specific accreditation or approval of professional preparation degree programs [3].

The accreditation system ensures high-level standards or best practices for distinguishing institutions that enjoy high autonomy or degree programs with relatively the same level of quality [7]. It provides a culture of periodic evaluations and identification of areas for improvement [8].

The accreditation process [3], [9] and certification from private and government institutions can measure and monitor the performance of various academic institutions. Developed countries are now reaping the benefits of the internationalization process while developing countries are forced to accept negotiations from them to get support in turn [10].

There are several monitoring teams that oversee international operations [11] which require colleges and universities to submit themselves for official visits to confirm and verify some documents and reports as proof that they follow the policies and guidelines set for them to ensure the delivery of quality education. Educational institutions allow external evaluators to examine their processes and results to identify several areas that will require further improvement and alignment with national and international demands from the industry and neighboring countries.

School accreditation is an evaluation activity carried out by the government and/or an independent institution. To determine the appropriateness of education programs and/or units in formal and non-formal education channels at every level and type of education, based on established criteria, as a form of public accountability carried out objectively, fairly, transparently, and comprehensively using instruments and criteria that refer to National Education Standards.

Systematic and comprehensive school accreditation through self-evaluation and external evaluation (visitation) activities to determine school eligibility and performance. Reason for school accreditation policies is that every citizen has the right to receive quality education. To be able to carry out quality education, each educational unit/program must meet or exceed standards carried out through accreditation activities on the suitability of each educational unit/program.

Accreditation can be seen as an instrument of self-regulation, with the intention that a School/Madrasah can understand the strengths and weaknesses of self; and based on an understanding of these strengths and weaknesses, Schools/Madrasah can make continuous quality improvements. Accreditation can also be seen as the result of an assessment in the form of formal certification of the condition of a School/Madrasah that has met certain service standards set by the government. In this perspective, there are Schools/Madrasah that are accredited and not, ranked A, B, C and so on.

There are 3 phases of the history of school accreditation in Indonesia. The first phase occurs when the Directorate of Private Schools of the Ministry of Education and Culture conducts accreditation of private schools. In this phase, school accreditation is only for private schools and seems very discriminatory. Especially with the ranking criteria as registered, recognized and equated. Private schools feel that they are always under position.

The second phase occurs when the National School Accreditation Board accredits all schools, both public and private, based on 9 (nine) components of school administration. The second phase of school accreditation system is considered unfair, due to the categorical and highly discrete nature of the instrument. Instrument response there are only two possible answers, which is between “yes” or “no”. If “yes”, then given a score of 1, whereas if “no” was given a score of “0”. It’s very discrete nature tends to ignore the qualitative, quantitative and functional ranges.

The third phase is marked by the implementation of school accreditation by the National Accreditation Board for Schools/Madrasah (BAN-S/M) with instruments compiled based on 8 (eight) National Education Standards. The third phase is an improvement and at the same time an answer to criticism from various parties over the weaknesses of the previous accreditation system. This is related to the growing awareness, that accreditation is not just a monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of learning activities in schools. Accreditation is carried out to determine the feasibility of programs and/or education units to demonstrate public accountability in education.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The research conducted is a descriptive study that aims to reveal the facts, the phenomenon, variables and circumstances that occur when the research takes place and presents what it is. The object of this study is elementary schools in Samarinda city, which is to examine self-evaluating of accreditation by the schools that become the sample. Research data type is primary data collected from the school accreditation team.

To find out how to assess school accreditation, the first thing to do is to conduct a self-assessment school. All items of statement of accreditation instruments for primary schools/madrasah ibtidaiyah which are closed statements must be answered by the school. There are five answer options, namely A, B, C, D, or E. The score conditions for each answer option are as follows: the item statement answered A gets a score of 4, the item statement answered B gets a score of 3, the

item statement answered C gets a score of 2, the item statement answered D gets a score of 1, and the item statement answered E gets a score of 0.

Then the maximum weighted score for each component of the accreditation is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Total Weighted Maximum Score} = \text{Maximum Item Score} \times \text{Number of Weighted Items}$$

The steps to determine the final accreditation score are as follows:

1. Converting each answer option A, B, C, D, or E into item scores. The instrument statements answered A get item scores of 4 (A=4), B=3, C=2, D=1, and E=0.
2. Enter the default weight item in the calculation table.
3. Calculate the Weighted Score for each item with the formula:

$$\text{Weighted Score} = \text{Item score} \times \text{weighted item}$$

4. Calculate the Weighted Score Amount by adding up the weighted scores of each item
5. Determine the Value of Accreditation Components with the formula:

$$\text{Accreditation Component Value} = \frac{\text{total weighted score}}{\text{max. weighted score}} \times \text{component weight}$$

6. Determine the Final Accreditation Score by adding up the entire Value of the Accreditation Component from component 1 (content standard) to component 8 (education assessment standard)
7. Final Accreditation Score must be written in integers without commas. The rounding provisions for the Final Accreditation Score are as follows:
 - a. If more than 0.05 rounded to 1;
 - b. If equal to 0.05 round up to 1; and
 - c. If it's less than 0.05 round to 0.

The hundred scale accreditation component value (0 – 100) is the percentage achievement value for each accreditation component. To determine the Hundred Scale Accreditation Component Value is the formula:

$$\text{Hundred Scale Accreditation Component Value} = \frac{\text{accreditation component value}}{\text{component weight}} \times 100$$

School/Madrasah accreditation status criteria are declared accredited if:

1. Obtains the Final Accreditation Result Score of at least 71
2. Obtains a Standard Component Value of Facilities and Infrastructure of not less than 61
3. There is no standard component value below 50

Schools/Madrasah are declared not accredited if they do not meet these criteria.

IV. FINDINGS RESEARCH / RESULTS

The primary school/madrasah ibtidaiyah accreditation instruments in Indonesia consist of (1) accreditation instruments, (2) technical guidelines for filling accreditation instruments, (3) data collection instruments and (4) information supporting accreditation and scoring techniques and ranking accreditation results. The four documents are an inseparable unit.

The primary school/madrasah ibtidaiyah accreditation

instrument includes eight components in accordance with national education standards [1]: the content standard component (10 points), the process standard component (21 points), the competency standard component (7 points) the standard component of educators and educational personnel (16 points), the standard component of facilities and infrastructure (21 points), the management standard component (15 points), the financing standard component (16 points) and the educational assessment standard component (13 points). Each school is asked to conduct a self-assessment and prepare all the physical evidence required in the technical guidelines for filling in the primary school/madrasah ibtidaiyah accreditation instrument and data collection instruments and supporting information for accreditation that will be used by the assessors when conducting clarification, verification and validation.

Accreditation ranking is done if the accreditation results meet the accreditation status criteria. Schools/Madrasah receive accreditation ratings as follows:

1. Accreditation rating A (Excellent) if the school/madrasah has a Final Accreditation Score (NA) of 91 to 100 ($91 \leq NA \leq 100$)
 2. Accreditation rating B (Good) if the school/madrasah has a Final Accreditation Score (NA) of 81 to 90 ($81 \leq NA \leq 90$)
 3. Accreditation rating C (Fair) if the school/madrasah has a Final Accreditation Score (NA) of 71 to 80 ($71 \leq NA \leq 80$)
- Schools/Madrasah that are not accredited are those who get the final grades:
1. Accreditation rating D (Less) if the school/madrasah has a Final Accreditation Score (NA) of 61 to 70 ($61 \leq NA \leq 70$)
 2. Accreditation rating E (Very Poor) if the school/madrasah has a Final Accreditation Score (NA) of 0 to 60 ($0 \leq NA \leq 60$)

The calculation results of final score of accreditation of each school are presented in table I to table IV.

TABLE I. The Results of Calculation of Final Score of Accreditation (School I)

No.	Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component (Scale of Hundreds)
1	Content Standards	13.34	95.27
2	Process Standard	12.90	92.16
3	Graduates' Competency Standards	12.38	88.46
4	Educator and Education Staff Standards	14.84	92.73
5	Facilities and Infrastructure Standards	9.70	80.83
6	Management Standards	10.00	100.00
7	Financing Standards	9.83	98.30
8	Educator Assessment Standards	9.84	98.37
Final Score of Accreditation (School I)		92.83	

Source: Data that has been processed

From the table above it can be seen that the Final Accreditation Score from the self-assessment process is equal to 93. Accreditation component score by hundreds scales in each component is greater than 50, and a facility and

infrastructure component value not less than 61, then the school is accredited with accreditation rating A (Excellent).

TABLE II. The Results of Calculation of Final Score of Accreditation (School II)

No.	Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component (Scale of Hundreds)
1	Content Standards	12.96	92.57
2	Process Standard	13.01	92.91
3	Graduates' Competency Standards	11.98	85.58
4	Educator and Education Staff Standards	15.56	97.27
5	Facilities and Infrastructure Standards	10.75	89.58
6	Management Standards	9.52	95.19
7	Financing Standards	10.00	100.00
8	Educator Assessment Standards	9.84	98.37
Final Score of Accreditation (School II)		93.62	

Source: Data that has been processed

From the table above it can be seen that the Final Accreditation Score from the self-assessment process is equal to 94. Accreditation component score by hundreds scales in each component is greater than 50, and a facility and infrastructure component value not less than 61, then the school is accredited with accreditation rating A (Excellent).

TABLE III. The Results of Calculation of Final Score of Accreditation (School III)

No.	Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component (Scale of Hundreds)
1	Content Standards	9.84	70.27
2	Process Standard	11.18	79.85
3	Graduates' Competency Standards	11.98	85.58
4	Educator and Education Staff Standards	11.56	72.27
5	Facilities and Infrastructure Standards	9.60	80.00
6	Management Standards	5.87	58.65
7	Financing Standards	7.61	76.14
8	Educator Assessment Standards	10.00	100.00
Final Score of Accreditation (School III)		77.64	

Source: Data that has been processed

From the table above it can be seen that the Final Accreditation Score from the self-assessment process is equal to 78. Accreditation component score by hundreds scales in each component is greater than 50, and a facility and infrastructure component value not less than 61, then the school is accredited with accreditation rating C (Fair).

From the table below it can be seen that the Final Accreditation Score from the self-assessment process is equal to 89. Accreditation component score by hundreds scales in each component is greater than 50, and a facility and infrastructure component value not less than 61, then the school is accredited with accreditation rating B (Good).

TABLE IV. The Results of Calculation of Final Score of Accreditation (School IV)

No.	Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component	Score of Accreditation Component (Scale of Hundreds)
1	Content Standards	13.62	97.30
2	Process Standard	13.69	97.76
3	Graduates' Competency Standards	11.44	81.73
4	Educator and Education Staff Standards	13.96	87.27
5	Facilities and Infrastructure Standards	7.45	62.08
6	Management Standards	9.47	94.71
7	Financing Standards	9.72	97.16
8	Educator Assessment Standards	10.00	100.00
Final Score of Accreditation (School IV)		89.35	

Source: Data that has been processed

There are two interesting things and can be further to analyzes from the findings of this study, management standards and facilities and infrastructure standards. There is an accreditation component of the two standards in the sample school which shows a low score, although it is still above the minimum required value.

Some schools are still experiencing problems with school management, especially when the data collection was done there turned out to be a sample schools that have experienced leadership changes. This of course has a very big impact on the process of managing these schools.

Related to facilities and infrastructure owned by schools is very dependent on the allocation of funds from the government (for public schools). Improvements of facilities and infrastructure requires a long time and cannot be fulfilled in a short time. However, schools can increase the value of other components of accreditation to get around the value of facilities and infrastructure standard that are still not good.

V. CONCLUSION

The completion of the accreditation instrument by the school/madrasah is the first step in the school accreditation assessment process. The process of clarification, verification and validation by the assessor team will be carried out at a next stage. Therefore, all physical evidence required in the technical instructions for filling the accreditation instrument and data collection and supporting accreditation instruments must be prepared by the school/madrasah.

Suggestions for further research can be developed to analyze the factors that influence the readiness of schools/madrasah in the school reaccreditation process.

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